

ANALYSIS OF HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT CONSTRAINTS AND ORGANIZATIONAL PRODUCTIVITY IN IMO STATE POLYTECHNIC, OMUMA

ADOLPHUS CHUKWUEMEKA ANORUO

*Department of Public Administration Imo State Polytechnic Omuma; Nigeria
Email:adolphuschukwuemeka@gmail.com; Phone No: +2347038820750*

NESTOR OBUMNEME OBIAKONWAMUO

*Department of Public Administration Imo State Polytechnic Omuma; Nigeria
Email: sirbumbu9@gmail.com, Phone Number: +2348030710862*

NJEMANZE, TOCHUKWU AMARACHI

*Department of Public Administration Imo State Polytechnic Omuma
Email: njemanze48@gmail.com, Phone number: 08068949922*

ABSTRACT

The study examined human capital development constraints to organizational productivity in Imo State polytechnic, Omuma. This is based on the importance of human capital in organizational productivity and the need for its development for a better organizational performance. It is upon these developments that the researchers constructed two research questions and objectives each to guide the study. Human Capital theory was used as a framework of analysis, with descriptive survey design adopted as the research design for the study. A sample size of 318 respondents selected from the population of 1553 staff of the institution was used. Simple random sampling technique that gives room for equal participation of all staff was further applied. The researchers used both primary and secondary data collection for the study. The primary data collections used were questionnaire administration and empirical review, while literature review was used as the secondary source of data. The data gathered were analyzed with the use of simple percentages, tables and Pearson Correlational Regression method to obtain result. The study found out that the constraints to human capital development in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, are; poor funding, poor infrastructure, administrative dependency; government influence, lack of adequate motivation, multi campus operation and so on. The study therefore, recommends that private sector should partner with government in providing infrastructural development in the institution. Also, the staff of institution should be motivated by the government and the management of the institution through provision of adequate welfare packages. These and others will enhance higher productivity in the institution.

Keywords: *Human capital, Human capital development, constraints, Productivity, Organization, Training*

1. INTRODUCTION

Education, skills acquisition, healthcare, expanded work experiences with creativity and innovations are the qualities that describe the capacity of personnel in an organization. These are the components of human capital development. Okojie, (1995) defines human capital as the abilities and skills of the human resource of an organization. Human capital encompasses all forms of skills, knowledge, competences, experience, education (schooling), healthcare, creativity, innovation, information and communication, and values that enable individual's social

development. It is the empowerment given on skill acquisition, knowledge building, education, and on the job and off the job trainings for organizational productivity. It is also a panacea for organizational productive performance. Ndinguri et al (2012) approached the study of human capital development as a course aiming towards improving values, team work and consciousness among individual employees to ensure overall performance of the organization. This informs World Bank (2021) in its human capital development enlightenment advised that countries should optimally invest on people to prevent the hard won human capital gains from being eroded more and also should build better to ensure green, resilient and inclusive development. Human capital is an innate, intricate and intangible value that enhances individual personality growth and development in institutions. Mike Gibbons, (2023) holds that human capital management is a collection of organizational practices related to the acquisition, management and development of human workforce or human capital within an organization.

Furthermore, this led Salsbury, (2013) to argue that human capital management is comprehensive because it includes not only human resource practices, but also other work practices and people management strategies that increase organizational performance. Human capital extends well beyond the human resource function to encompass the total people strategy of the organization. It is owned by all business leaders and resides with everyone in the organization. Kucharekova, (2011) asserts that human capital influences the economic growth through expansion of the knowledge and skills of the resource persons. The levels of economic growth are determined by the amount of skilled labour needed. Human capital is the totality of person knowledge and skills the economy can use to continue the achievement of its goals. Dess and Picken (1999) argue further that human capital consists of the individual's capabilities, knowledge, skills and experience of the company's employees and managers, as they are relevant to the task at hand as well as the capacity to add to this reservoir of knowledge, skills and experience through individual learning. This is a reflective of human capacity building in Imo State Polytechnic (Omuma) that have been enjoying the efficacy of human capital development. However, despite the enormity of valuable trained personnel in the institution, Imo State Polytechnic Omuma has been facing daunting task on human capital development in other areas. The poor infrastructure, poor incentive for workers motivation, inadequate healthcare services due to absence of hospitals, insecurity around the campuses and lack of pension after service are the subjects of concern in the institution.

Owing to the above development, this research work was conducted to analyze the constraints of human capital development to organizational productivity in the Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma. This motivated the researchers into this research work with the following objectives:

1. To analyze the constraints of human capital development to organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma.
2. To examine the strategies towards addressing human capital development constraints in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma.

Research Questions

1. What are the constraints of human capital development in organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma?
2. What are the strategies towards addressing human capital development constraints in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma?

The studies will however, be beneficial to both public and private sectors and organizations. It addresses economic challenges; improvement in skills, knowledge acquisition and creativity needed to improve socio-economic development through the provision of employment/appointment, reduction of poverty and ignorance, provision of infrastructural

facilities. It can as well improve healthcare and international cooperation through knowledge building, creativity, skills and outputs production.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Capital

Human capital encompasses all forms of skills, knowledge, competences, experience, education, healthcare, creativity, innovation, information and communication, and values that enables individual social development. World Bank (2021) states that countries invest in people optimally to prevent the hard won human capital gains from being eroded more and build back better to ensure green, resilient and inclusive development. Human capital is an innate, intricate and intangible value that enhances individual personality growth and development. Becker (1993) conceived that human capital includes investment in education, training, skills, health and other values that cannot be separated from individual.

Human Capital Development

Human capital development is the series of the trainings given for manpower development in the organization. Throughout the whole human history; several major shifts and upheavals occurred that fundamentally transformed social and economic relations and contribute towards shaping up of the human capital. These changes impacted on the innovation and the development of knowledge and the formation of the world order (Hippe 2020; Surya et al, 2020). Schooling, expenditure on medical care and lectures on the virtues of punctuality and honesty are capital. This is because, they raise the earnings, improve health or add to a person's lifetime, expenditure on education, trainings and other values acquiring knowledge and investment on human capital (Becker, 2011).

Constraints of Human Capital Development to Organizational Productivity

Constraints are the difficulties, perils and challenges that bedeviled human resource persons and organizations from achieving its full potentials towards productive performance. Lahuschanget Kleynhans, (2012) explored the potential human capital constraints in the South African economy. Human capital constraints are aspect of human capital that limit the productivity and effectiveness of the workforce. The work indicated that;

(i) Inadequate educated workforce, and (ii) Restrictive labour regulations, are the two major human capital constraints facing the South African economy.

In the same vein, in Nigeria, there are constraints of human capital development according to the executive secretary, Universal Basic Education Commission, Dr. Hamid Bobboyi, (News Agency of Nigeria, 2021). They include:

- i. Shortage of workforce: Accordiwnng to Dr Hamid Bobboyi(date), quoting the Executive Secretary, Universal Basic Education Commission, states thatthe shortage of teachers in basic education sector affects human capital development. The benefits of investing in education were shown to be a form of capital, which is human capital. An empirical evidence indicates that there is a positive relationship between educational attainment and output per worker and therefore productivity.
- ii. Inadequate financing of project: Lack of funds or resources to carry out projects affects the human capital development. Projects like education, skill acquisition and infrastructural development might be problematic to any organization that lack equipped workforce to carry out the functions designated.

- iii. **Poor Infrastructure:** This includes road network, electrification, pipeborne water/bore hole, standard hospitals and schools. The availability of these infrastructural facilities helps improve effective human capital development, such as enhancing training of workers, easy and smooth movement of personnel and officials for services. Where there are poor infrastructural facilities; the system malfunction and poor result will be witnessed in the organization.
- iv. **Poor workers motivation:** When workers are not motivated, even with returns on investment, profitability, and effective and efficient services; they will feel discouraged and demoralized at the work place. The poor and inadequate salaries/wages, bonuses, allowances and other welfare packages will affect workers' performance.
- v. **Unfavorable policy formulation and implementation:** Public policies should be made to promote manpower planning and implementation, but when such government policies like downsizing of workforce; and some others that do not encourage and reward hard work are made, they tend to demoralize workers for higher efforts in organizations, thereby constituting constraints to human capital development.

Similarly, Caitlin Kapolas (2024) outlined the challenges of human capital management as follows:

- i. Lack of employee retention and turnover
- ii. Restrictive compliance with labour law and regulations
- iii. Low engagement of employee undermines productivity
- iv. Inability to provide convincing feedback affects performance management in the organization.

Also Lisa Schawz, (2025) gave the challenges of human capital management as:

- i. Inability to attract and retain top talent in the organization
- ii. Difficult in align with the people strategies with business strategies
- iii. Difficult managing a multi-generational workforce

All the above challenges of human capital development to organizational development, if not managed properly may hinder the objectives of any organization.

2.1 THEORETICAL LITERATURE

The study is embedded on human capital theory, conceived and developed by three prominent proponents; Jacob Mincer, (1958); Theodore Schultz, (1961) and Gary Stanley Becker, (1964). Human Capital theory was fundamentally rooted from macro-economic development theory captured in Becker's classic book captioned "Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis of Education". In the theory, Becker viewed different kinds of capitals which include; schooling, computer training courses, expenditure on medical care, important of punctuality and honesty as indicators that improve health, raise earnings and add values to personality thereby enhances productive performance. Becker opines that investment in human could be viewed as similar to investment in other means of production like factories or mines. That is because they raise the earnings, improve health and add to a person's lifetime. This is because; economists' regard expenditures on education, training and medical care as investment on human capital (Becker, 2011). He further stressed that economic growth cannot be explained by the growth of physical capital and technological innovation rather the growth of human capital. Becker, (1993) distinguishes firm specific human capitals from general purpose human capital. The firm specific human capital include expertise obtained through education and training in management information systems, accounting procedures or other expertise specific to a particular firm. The

general purpose human capital is knowledge gained through education and training in areas of value to a variety of firms such as generic skills in human resource development.

In developing Becker's work further, another economist, Theodore Schultz, (1961) contends that a society should invest in its citizens through expenditures on education, training, research and health that enhance their productive capacity. He believes that human capital is the added value that people bring in an organization. Schultz (1979) opines that human capital involves the increase investment in education and training of the individuals, and individual abilities can be enhanced through education and training that bring about effective change in the performance of jobs. In his further studies, he set out to map out how the rate of return from education could be calculated in countries with different levels of income, different attitudes to forgoing earnings to develop human capital (Severine and Lila, 2009). Therefore, it is consented that the theory acknowledges well trained personnel as a great asset to organizations. It is a potential base of an organization that gives it a competitive advantage over others. Schultz, (1981), took into account the innate and acquired skills that are important and may be invested on to expand and form the human capital. So, investing in people (human capital) is the one of the major sources of economic growth in a modern economy'. He maintains that investing in skills and innate values promote organizational productivity. Human Capital theory is a theory on finance and economics. It articulates that companies should have incentives to promote the human capital of their existing employees. It is also a concept that recognizes labour capital and posits that human beings can increase their productive capacity through greater education and skills training. The theory further analyzes that as the world build up on physical capital, the opportunity cost of going to school reduced. This makes education vital component of the workforce to promote innovation and creativity.

Jacob Mincer was considered by many as the father of the modern labour economics. He was one of the leading members of Chicago school of economists, whose work 'Investment in Human Capital and Personal Income Distribution', in his journal of Political Economy (1958) attracted much profound impact. He accompanied Gary Becker in the development of empirical foundations of human capital theory and revolutionizes the field of labour economics. His ground breaking work was on schooling, experience and earning published in (1974) used data from 1950 and 1960 censuses to relate income distribution in America to the varying amounts of education and on the job training among workers. In his calculations, annual earnings rose by 5 to 10 percent in the 1950s and 1960s for every year of additional schooling. Mincer's work impacted greatly to labour economics, thereby modeling wages as a function of human capital in statistical estimation. That made Mincer's work such as schooling and work experience as variables use in measuring human capital. However, it is very clear that human capital is all about the employees and not the employers. His very simple formulation basically fits the data for understanding how earnings are related to educational attainment in virtually every country in every time period (Lawrence, 2006)

2.2 EMPIRICAL REVIEW

In empirical studies, Lahuschang et Kleynhans, (2012) explored the potential human capital constraints in the South African economy. The study holds that human capital constraints are difficult that limit the productivity and effectiveness of the workforce. The work indicated that inadequate educated workforce and restrictive labour regulations are the two major human capital constraints facing the South African economy. In relation to Imo state polytechnic, Omuma, Nigeria, some government policies such as; poor workers motivation, inadequate funding of projects and insecurity around the school are the constraints of human capital development in the

institution. Generally in Nigeria, shortage of both primary and secondary school teachers affects human capital development. For instance; there have been statistical records of shortage of 2,777, 537 teachers in basic education sector in Nigeria as was pointed out by the executive secretary, Universal Basic Education Commission, Dr. Hamid Bobboyi, (News agency of Nigeria 2021). Investing in education is shown to be a form of capital development. Human capital empirical evidence indicates that there is a positive relationship between educational attainment and output per worker and therefore productivity.

Alika and Aibreya, (2014) exposed some of the errors of writers in omitting “commitment” in their list of the characteristics of human capital of which considers skills, knowledge, and experience as the main important to it. No matter the amount of skills, knowledge and experience gathered without “commitment” to perform creditably on the given task, there still going to be inefficiency in spite of the possession of the requisite mental-social-psychological and economic aptitudes. Relating this study to human capital constraints in Imo State Polytechnic, the government of the state is to be blamed for neglecting human capital development in the institution, even when the workers are putting in enough effort for the growth of the institution.

In a study by Adejumo and Adejumo, (2017) to address the direction of casualty between human capital and productivity growth in Nigeria, the study first investigated the pattern of productivity growth in Nigeria and the casual relation between human capital development and productivity growth in Nigeria using the Engle-Granger causality test. The results revealed that productivity growth has been very low and unstable in Nigeria. The nexus between human capital and productivity growth was examined. The findings revealed that while productivity growth caused human capital development, human capital development did not cause productivity growth. This study explains the true picture of Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma where the human capital growth does not cause productivity, while productivity growth causes human capital development. This is observed due to low enrolment of students, insecurity and government negligence of the institution in providing funds for projects.

3. METHODOLOGY

Survey research design is used in this study. It involves procedures outline for the conduct of any given investigation. Survey research design is adopted due to its descriptive nature of research analyzing. The population of the study is 1553 staff with sample size of 318 respondents selected, calculated with Taro Yamane formula. The simple random sampling technique was also used to give all the staff equal change of being selected. In determining the sample size of the study, the formula was followed thus;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+Nx(e)^2} \quad n = \frac{1553}{1+1553(5)^2} \quad n = \frac{1553}{1+1553(0.05)^2} \quad n = \frac{1553}{1+1553x0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{1553}{1 + 1553x 0.0025} \quad n = \frac{1553}{1 + 3883} \quad n = \frac{1553}{4.883} \quad n = 318 \quad n = 318$$

The two methods used in data collection are the primary data collection and secondary data collection. The primary data collection involves the gathering of information through questionnaire and empirical study, while the secondary data collection involves the review of the

related literature which is done by extracting information from textbooks, journals; internet explores materials and newspapers.

The researchers adopted face/content validity and construct validity to measure instruments. In the face validity, well-structured questionnaire instrument was used to gather information from the respondents. The researchers also ensured that the items in the questionnaire were in conformity with the items in the objectives of the study, research questions and research hypothesis which are the representativeness of sampling adequacy of the content (the substance, the topic, the issue). The researchers also constructed instrument of response for the respondents in a four (4) likert scale. The test-retest method was used to confirm the reliability of the instrument for the study. The consistency, dependability and credibility of the questionnaire items administered and the responses given by the respondents during questionnaire administration proved reliability of the instrument. Here, the instrument has produced consistency the same result over time. In the first test, the researchers distributed 150 copies of the questionnaire to the public (Imo State Polytechnic staff), but 141 copies were recovered and recorded. In two weeks' time, the same number of copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the same group of people as was done in the first test. Out of 150 copies of the questionnaire, 145 copies were recovered and recorded. While analyzing the responses to the questionnaire recovered, it was observed that the respondents maintained consistent views overtime and that the results correlated with the earlier test results. This implies that there is high coefficient of correlations between the two results.

Statistical tables and percentages, Statistical Mean, Standard Deviation and Pearson Correlation Coefficient were used to present data gathered, while SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) was however used in data analysis. The study concludes that the results of the tests are reliable.

3.1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Human Capital theory by leading proponents, such as; Jacob Mincer, (1958), Theodore Schultz, (1961) and Gary Stanley Becker (1964) was used as a framework of analysis. Human Capital theory is fundamentally rooted from macro-economic development theory captured in Becker's classic book captioned "Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis of Education". The theory assumes that the composition of the employee in form of skills, knowledge, and abilities is the key to organizational performance. It went on to state that investing in skills and innate values promote organizational productivity. Human capital is also a concept that recognizes labour capital and posits that human beings can increase their productive capacity through greater education and skills training. Human capital development however, is the employee knowledge, skills, knowledge, good health and education that enhances personal and organizational productivity. Organizations invest in its citizens through expenditures on education, training, research and health that enhance their productive capacity. Human capital is the added value that people bring in an organization.

Strengths of Human Capital Theory in Education and Policy Making

1. It is used in education research and policy making. It helps the policy makers and researchers to evaluate the relationship between the educations and training as inputs and economic and social benefits as outputs. Since the assumption stated that increase amount of schooling will bring growth in higher individual wages, Gross domestic product and increase in citizens participation, crime reduction and adequate healthcare services. Therefore, this enables the policy makers evaluate relatively the efficiency of public programs that encourage education

2. It provides a useful avenue for understanding how policy can be developed to promote individuals investment in their education. It reviews that embarking in further education (schooling) involves both cost that is spending (sacrificing at present and benefiting through higher wages in future) within individual level. Therefore, adopting human capital theory in this study will help the policy makers develop rational policies geared towards providing avenues for students’ loan and enrolment programmes to change individual costs and benefits calculation by reducing the short costs in order to encourage the likelihood of pursuing education increasingly.
3. Human capital theory can be used to address individual social investments in education, such as the quality knowledge/investment in education that are productive and the best time for education and policy development best to reduce the costs of education.
4. It helps to increase the creative and innovative knowledge and how to utilize the knowledge to further productivity, investment, growth and development of the society.

Adopting human capital theory and principles in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, will enhance knowledge; skills and education which provide sustainability and development thereby providing opportunities for future generation of staff and students. It will go on to provide good opportunity for education and trainings among individual staff and the institution in general, thereby promoting economic growth and productivity. This is because; long term economic growth depends to greater extent on the improvement on human capital. A good education, creativity or innovative workforce fosters labour productivity and economic growth and development. Furthermore, building upon the human capital theory enables knowledge and trainings that can lead to provision of quality employment and promotion in the institution. This is because the acquisition of high skilled and creative workforce will increase opportunities for higher promotions in the Polytechnic. Finally, adopting the principles of Human Capital theory will enable the beneficiaries of the abilities who are surrounding with limited raw materials to utilize their skills and knowledge in order to ensure better development of Polytechnic community

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The data presentation, analysis and interpretation were done with the use of simple percentage, mean, standard deviation and Pearson correlation regression analysis. The study started with the analysis of the sex of the respondents, designation, and marital status, age bracket of the respondents and educational qualification of the respondents. Others are the data presentation, analysis and interpretation with hypothetical analysis of the study. Bellows are the tables:

Table 1: Questionnaire Distribution and Return Rates

Response	Number Distributed	%	Number Returned	%	Number not Returned	%
Teaching Staff	149	47	134	42	15	5
Non-teaching Staff	169	53	151	47	18	5.7
Total	318	100	285	89	24	11

Source: field study, 2025

The table 1 represents the questionnaire administration. Here, 318 copies of questionnaire were administered to the respondents. Out of 318 copies of questionnaire administered 285 (89%) were completed and returned, while 33 (11%) were not returned. This suggests that a very high percentage of copies of the questionnaire were returned.

Table 4.2 Demographic Representation of the Respondents

Parameter	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	140	49.1
	Female	145	50.9
	Total	285	100
Age	18-25	3	1.1
	26-35	107	37.5
	36-45	142	49.8
	46-55	31	10.9
	56-65	2	0.7
	Total	285	100
	Educational Qualifications	PhD	10
	M.Sc	123	43.2
	B.Sc/B.ED	96	33.7
	HND	38	13.36
	Others	18	6.3
	Total	285	100
Designation	Academic Staff	136	47.7
	Non-Academic staff	149	52.3
	Total	285	100
Marital Status	Single	15	5.3
	Married	256	89.8
	Separated	12	4.2
	Widowed	2	0.7
	Total	285	100

Source: field study, 2025

Base on questionnaire administered, out of 285 respondents; 140 respondents representing (49.1%) are male while 145 respondents representing (50.9%) are female staff respectively.

Considering the age distribution of the respondents above, the respondents between the ages of 18 years and 30 years old were 3 (1.1%). The respondents between 31 years and 40 years old were 107 (37.5%), while the respondents between the ages of 41 years and 50 years were 142(49.8%). The respondents between the ages of 51 years and 60 years were 33 (10.9%), and the respondents between the ages of 60years and above were 2 (0.7%). This shows that the respondents between the ages of 41 years and 50 years were the highest in number. Consequently, the Polytechnic is made up of middle aged workers.

The job status of the respondents shows that out of 285 respondents in the research study, 136 (47.7%) respondents were teaching staff of the Polytechnic, while 149(52.3%) were non-teaching staff. On the marital status of the respondents, 15 (5.3%) were single, 256 (89.8%) were married, 12 (4.2%) were separated, while 2 (0.7%) were widowed.

Question 1: What are the constraints of human capital development to organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic Omuma?

Table 2

S/N	(Questionnaire Options)	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree
1.	The Constraints Of Human Capital Development to Organizational Productivity In Imo State Polytechnic Omuma				
(A)	Poor Motivation and Inadequate Healthcare Service	190(67)	81(28.4)	5(1.8%)	9{3.2}
(B)	Poor funding	118(41.4)	154(54)	7(2.5%)	6(2%)
(C)	Poor/Absence of Infrastructural Development	185(65%)	88(31%)	2(0.7%)	10(3.5%)
(D)	Leadership Problems/ Government Undue Interference	71(25%)	99(35%)	20(7%)	95(33%)
(E)	Insecurity	121(42.5%)	149(52.3%)	4(1.4%)	11(4%)

Source: field work, 2025

In research question 1 option A, it was articulated that 190 (67%)and 81 (28.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively that poor motivation and healthcare services remains the constraints of human capital in Imo State Polytechnic Omuma, while 5 (1.8%) and 9 (3.2) of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively. This however, shows that poor motivation and inadequate healthcare services are constraints of human capital development in the institution.

In research question 1 options B, the findings showed that poor funding affected human capital development in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma. 118(41.4%) and 154 (54%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively, while 7(2.5%) and 6 (2%) of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively to the above assertion.

Again, in research question 1option C, 185 (65%) and 88 (31%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed, that poor/absence of infrastructural development affected human capital development in Imo State Polytechnic Omuma, while 2 (0.7%) and 10 (31%) of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively to the assertion. This then shows that poor/absence of infrastructural development affected human capital development in institution.

Furthermore, in research question 1 option D, 71 (25%) and 99 (35%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively that leadership problems/government undue interference and insecurity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma affected human capital development of the in the institution, while 20 (7%) and 95 (33%) of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively to the assertion. This entails that leadership problems, government undue interference and insecurity are constraints to human capital development in the institution.

In research question one option E, 121 respondents representing (42.5%) strongly agreed that insecurity affect human capital development in Imo state polytechnic. 149 respondents representing (52%) of the respondents agreed with the notion, while 4(1.4%) respondents strongly disagreed and 11(4%) of the entire respondents disagreed respectively. Therefore, the total of 270

representing 94.5% out of 285 respondents sounded positive that insecurity affect human capital development in Imo state polytechnic, while 15 respondents representing 5.4% of the entire respondents sounded negative to the effect respectively.

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS

Research Question 1: What are the constraints of human capital development to organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma?

Table 3: Mean responses on the Constraints of Human Capital Development to Organizational Productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Remark
i.	Employers do not provide adequate resources to support human capital development	55	145	71	14	2.84	0.789	Agreed
ii	There is a lack of qualified human capital in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma	59	130	87	9	2.84	0.78	Disagreed
ii	Organizational policies and procedures do not support human capital development	74	130	72	9	2.94	0.80	Agreed
iv	Poor motivation and remuneration	47	106	80	52	2.52	0.97	Agreed
v	Poor/absence of infrastructural development	24	257	4	--	3.07	0.31	Agreed
v	Leadership problems and government undue interference	62	178	30	15	3.01	0.73	Agreed
v	The government do not provide adequate security to support human capital development	142	47	42	54	2.97	1.19	Agreed
Grand Mean						2.88	0.80	Agreed

.Table indicated the constraints of human capital development to organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma. The table accounted that the constraints of human capital development to organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma are lack of qualified human capital (mean=2.84, Std.=0.78), poor motivation and healthcare services (Mean=2.52, Std.=0.97), poor/absence of infrastructural development (mean=3.07, Std.=0.31), leadership problems/government undue interference and insecurity (mean=3.01, std.=0.73). Also, the table captured that inadequate provision of resources to support human capital development by the state government as contributes to the constraints of human capacity development.

Table 4: Relationship between Constraints of Human Capital Developments and Organizational Productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma
Correlations

		ConstraintsofHumanCapitalDe velopment	OrganizationalProd uctivity
ConstraintsofHumanCapitalDe velopment	Pearson Correlat ion	1	-.685**
	Sig. (2- tailed)		.000
	N	285	285
OrganizationalProductivity	Pearson Correlat ion	-.685**	1
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.000	
	N	285	285

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 shows the summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis on the relationship between constraints of human capital developments and organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma. The result shows the value of the R-square -0.685 was roughly 68.5% constraints of human capital developments to organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma. The result also shows that the p (significant value=0.00 is less than 0.05 at 285 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. Therefore, there is a significant negative relationship between human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma.

4.1DISCUSSIONOF FINDINGS

Research question 1 examined the constraints of human capital development to organizational productivity in Imo state polytechnic. The results of the study showed that lack of qualified human capital (mean=2.84, std.=0.78), poor motivation and remuneration (mean=2.52, std.=0.97), poor/absence of infrastructural development (mean=3.07, std.=0.31), leadership problems/government undue interference and Insecurity (mean=3.01, std.=0.73) and inadequate provision of resources to support human capital development by the government and the management of the institution contribute to the constraints of human capital development to organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma. In the same vein, its corresponding hypothesis shows a significant negative relationship between human capital development and organizational productivity in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma (r=0.685, at 0.05 level of significance).

Leadership problem/Undue political interference and Insecurity: Imposition of candidates and negligence of the due process in public service appointments and promotions affect public service activities negatively. It is dependent instead on a partially autonomous entity. For instance; indiscriminate appointment of staff to office without due consultation to the law (code of conduct, rules and regulations) affect the system from achieving the desired needs and aspirations of the organization. The process of appointment is marred by corruption and ineptitude attitudes that

have affected the contents and quality of policies at formulation stage, leading to consequent implementation of such policies by public administrators.

Lack/inadequate motivational packages: When a worker is not motivated to work due to the inability of the government to pay the adequate salaries, wages and other remuneration regularly and this demoralizes workers, leading to workers ineffectiveness and inefficiency in service. The inability of the government to provide the public servants with adequate welfare packages such as; leave allowances, healthcare services, provision of accommodation, gratuities, provision of educational training and development affect the institution. Any factor that hinders the government from working according to the country's rules of engagement of its workforce will certainly affect the performance of the public service from discharging its functions. Unfavorable economic states affect the conditions in the society such as a high cost of living. Consequently, inadequate salaries and wages have contributed greatly to the challenges of the Imo State Polytechnic in particular and public service in general. Salisu (2001), assert that many attempts have been made to increase the minimum wages of Nigerian workers, but all the attempts have not yielded much desired impact in the living conditions of the workers. For instance, the recent increment of Imo State workers' minimum wage by Governor Hope Uzodinma administration has been lauded but also criticized for not addressing the economic realities of the workers.

Poor Funding: The institution is highly poor funded. These affect the provision of infrastructures, administrative services and socio-economic arrangement which will aid in realizing the organization efficiency and capacity building. Many findings have been made in this regard. It is observed that **poor motivation and remuneration of personnel** of both public and private sectors are one of the constraints of human capital development and capacity building in our organization. The inadequate/absence of staff training scheme, poor/irregular payment of workers entitlements (salaries, wages, bonuses, leave allowance, housing allowance, furniture allowance and overtimes and poor salary/ wages structure) and absence of implementation of the standard structure are the limitations observed.

Poor healthcare services: Poor quality healthcare services affect people's wellbeing. Poor feeding and lack of quality food due to poor remuneration affect abilities to cope with learning, trainings, skills acquisition, competence development and values integration of workers in the organization.

Poor/absence of infrastructural facilities: inadequate electrification, lack of water supply, inadequate hospitals, maternity and health centres, poor school system, poor road network, and insufficient housing scheme as infrastructures are some of constraints of human capital development in the institution.

Corruption: This includes unnecessary delay in attending to files, given attention to deserving individuals due to sectional interest, hatred, undue sentiments, favouritism, nepotism, jealousy and segregation among the staff in the institution.

Insecurity: The killings, robberies, raping and environmental upheaval ravaging the environment of the Polytechnic are threats to enhancement of human capital development in the institution.

Brain Drain: This is a situation whereby the intellectuals/ trained professionals are leaving their institution to settle in another area due to insecurity, unemployment, inadequate protection of jobs and poor salaries. This is the movement of the intellectuals across border in search of greener

pastures. It is the migration of human capital potentials across the border for the purpose of hunting for opportunities and survival.

Irregular promotion of the employees: Irregular promotion of the staff of Polytechnic can hinder the utilization of the human capital in the institution.

4.2 CONCLUSION

Human capital development has been adjudged as a panacea for organizational productive performance particularly in Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma. This is as a result of the increasing skills, knowledge, system thinking, creativity and innovative skills, leadership and management abilities, strategic thinking, decision making skill and problem solving skills, its research ability and diligence effort towards human and material development, problems solving and capacity building.

However, based on empirical study (evidence), the study concluded that the constraints of human capital development have socio-economic and political effects; such as poor health care services, leadership problems, inadequate infrastructural development, unemployment and joblessness, government interference, inadequate nutrition services, poor educational standard and school enrolment, lack of awareness and inequality in wealth, poor training and development, inadequate manpower planning, Brain drain, absence of industrialization, poor motivation, lack of professionalism and specialization, negligence of culture and values and multi campuses operation with poor funding.

4.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study; the following recommendations are made;

1. The government should as a matter of fact ensure adequate motivation and remuneration of staff regularly by routine training and development and regular payments of salaries and remuneration. This will improve morale capacity to work hard, committed spirit of service and effective and efficient service delivery in the institution.
2. Government should ensure the provision of adequate health care services by providing more healthcare facilities and employ well trained personnel in the hospitals that will facilitate the effective and efficient delivery of health care services to the public and ensure capacity building in the institution.
3. Both government and private sectors should as a matter of fact join hands in providing adequate infrastructural facilities such as; good road network, electricity, adequate water supply. Hospitals and other health centres, and so on, for the wellbeing of the people.
4. The policies of the government should be geared towards promotion of human capital development in public institution
5. Government is advised to desist from unnecessary interference in the activities of Imo State Polytechnic to enable the management concentrate on service delivery.
6. Imo State Polytechnic as an institution should ensure corrupt free environment devoid of exploitation, misappropriation of funds, mismanagement and malpractices which endanger socio-economic development in the institution.
7. The institution should as a matter of fact adopt adequate disciplinary measures towards ensuring sanity and sanctity, order and discipline, capable of ensuring effective and efficient productive performance in the institution.

8. There should be continues training and retraining of human resources (workers) by providing more scholarship opportunities and ensures adequate and standardized training services.

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